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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
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- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
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- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING A SCHEDULE FOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article highlights the pedagogical and psychological importance of forming a daily routine in high school students. The role of a daily schedule in improving students' academic performance, maintaining health, effective time management, and developing independent learning skills is analyzed. In addition, cooperation between parents and educational institutions is considered an important factor in the comprehensive development of a student's personality. During the research, theoretical analysis and pedagogical observation methods were used. The conclusions of the article substantiate that establishing a regular daily routine among high school students contributes to improving the quality of education and the effectiveness of the educational process.

Key words: daily routine, nervous system, fatigue, overfatigue, attention, mental load, physical load, coordination, dynamic stereotype, immunity, physical activity, vitality, hygiene, sleep.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida kun tartibini shakllantirishning pedagogik va psixologik ahamiyati yoritilgan. Kun tartibining o'quvchilarning o'zlashtirish darajasini oshirish, sog'lig'ini saqlash, vaqtni samarali boshqarish hamda mustaqil ta'lim olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, ota-onalar va ta'lim muassasalari hamkorligi o'quvchi shaxsining har tomonlama rivojlanishida muhim omil sifatida ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot jarayonida nazariy tahlil va pedagogik kuzatish metodlaridan foydalanilgan. Maqola xulosalarida yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida muntazam kun tartibini shakllantirish ta'lim sifati va tarbiyaviy jarayon samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qilishi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kun tartibi, asab tizimi, charchoq, o'ta charchash, diqqat, aqliy yuklama, jismoniy yuklama, muvofiqlashtirish, dinamik stereotip, immunitet, jismoniy faollik, tetiklik, gigiyena, uyqu.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещается педагогическое и психологическое значение формирования режима дня у учащихся старших классов. Проанализирована роль режима дня в повышении успеваемости учащихся, сохранении здоровья, эффективном управлении временем и развитии навыков самостоятельного обучения. Кроме того, сотрудничество родителей и образовательных учреждений рассматривается как важный фактор всестороннего развития личности учащегося. В ходе исследования использовались методы теоретического анализа и педагогического наблюдения. В выводах статьи обосновано, что формирование регулярного режима дня у старшеклассников способствует повышению качества образования и эффективности воспитательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: режим дня, нервная система, утомление, переутомление, внимание, умственная нагрузка, физическая нагрузка, координация, динамический стереотип, иммунитет, физическая активность, бодрость, гигиена, сон.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, significant changes are being observed in the field of education. The organization and modernization of an educational process that meets global standards are contributing to increased effectiveness. Today, improving the academic performance of high school students is considered one of the most important issues in the education system. Students' learning achievement, independent thinking, and physical and mental health largely depend on their daily routine. A properly structured daily schedule helps students allocate their time rationally, maintain a balance between study and rest, and achieve their goals. In particular, forming a daily routine plays an important role in preparing high school students for independent life. Therefore, this article examines the importance of forming a daily routine in high school students and its impact on the educational process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of organizing students' daily routines has long attracted the attention of educators, psychologists, and physiologists. Researchers emphasize that a properly structured daily schedule contributes not only to academic achievement but also to the physical and psychological well-being of students.

The scientific foundations of daily routine organization are closely connected with the works of I. P. Pavlov. His theory of higher nervous activity explains the importance of maintaining a balanced alternation between mental work, physical activity, rest, and sleep. According to Pavlov, regular repetition of activities at specific times contributes to the formation of dynamic stereotypes, which increase the efficiency of the nervous system and improve learning performance.

Studies in educational psychology indicate that students who follow a regular daily routine demonstrate higher levels of concentration, self-discipline, and academic motivation. Researchers have found that proper time management enables learners to complete educational tasks more effectively and reduces the negative effects of mental fatigue.

Health-related studies also highlight the importance of sufficient sleep and physical activity for adolescents. According to various physiological investigations, a balanced schedule that includes adequate sleep, regular meals, and physical exercise supports cognitive development, strengthens immunity, and improves emotional stability. Conversely, irregular daily routines are associated with increased stress, reduced attention span, and lower academic performance.

Recent educational research emphasizes the role of parents and schools in developing healthy daily habits among students. Effective cooperation between families and educational institutions creates favorable conditions for establishing responsible behavior, independent learning skills, and positive attitudes toward education.

Therefore, the existing literature confirms that the formation of a well-organized daily routine is an important pedagogical and psychological factor influencing students' academic success, personal development, and overall well-being.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examined the impact of forming a daily routine in high school students on learning activity, effective time management, and personal development. Students from grades 9-11 of general education schools were selected as the research material. During the study, pedagogical, psychological, and methodological literature was analyzed. In addition, survey and interview methods were used to determine students' daily routines, attitudes toward studying, and the level of organization of their free time. Through questionnaires, students' planning of study and rest time, adherence to sleep schedules, and use of technology were investigated.

I. P. Pavlov's doctrine on higher nervous activity and the coordinating and regulatory functions of the central nervous system provides a scientific basis for organizing a daily routine in such a way that the alternation of work and rest, as well as the sequence of different types of activities, is taken into account. When studying students' daily routines and academic workload, one of the most relevant issues is maintaining physiological balance in the organism through the combination of various activities, such as rest, nutrition, sleep, and others. This ensures a faster restoration of students' working capacity [1, 5, 6].

In the study, the observation method was used to analyze students' daily activities, classroom engagement, and discipline. Using the comparison method, the academic performance of students who consistently followed a daily routine was compared with that of those who did not adhere to such a schedule.

In the process of generalizing and analyzing the obtained data, the methods of analysis and synthesis were applied. Based on the results, conclusions were drawn regarding the formation of a daily routine in high school students, and practical recommendations were developed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In order to study the formation of a daily routine among high school students, research was conducted in Secondary School No. 13 located in the Qibray District of the Tashkent Region. Students in grades 9-11 were selected as the research object. A questionnaire survey was carried out to determine students' daily routines and their level of adherence to them (Table 1).

Table 1: Preliminary Analysis of the Level of Adherence to the Daily Routine among 9th-Grade Students of Secondary School No. 13 in the Qibray District (Experimental Group)

Grade 9 "A" / 20 students			Grade 9 "B" / 22 students		
It works	Partially valid	Doesn't work	It works	Partially valid	Doesn't work
2 (10%)	6 (30%)	12 (60%)	3 (13,6 %)	6 (27,3 %)	13 (59,1%)

The results of the study showed that adherence to a daily routine among high school students directly affects the effectiveness of the learning process. It was found that students with a regular and well-organized daily routine completed lessons on time, approached classes responsibly, and demonstrated a higher level of achievement.

As a result of the questionnaire and observations, it was observed that students who planned their daily routines were more active in class, had better concentration, and developed independent work skills. On the contrary, students who did not follow a daily routine were more likely to become tired, waste time, and be late for classes. The study also found that the proper distribution of sleep and rest time has a positive effect on the physical and mental well-being of students. Students who followed a daily routine had lower stress levels, higher self-confidence, and a stronger sense of discipline.

CONCLUSION

The daily schedule must include “free time”- hours when the child can do whatever he wants. This helps the child learn and develop his interests. Scientists say that although the daily routine formed in childhood does not directly affect a person’s IQ (intellectual potential), it can increase his EQ (emotional intelligence) and success in life by up to 40%. This is because success is 1% talent and 99% hard work (discipline). The last part of the daily schedule should be “the end of the day.” This teaches the student the following (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Questions That Arise in Students Throughout the Day

Answering these questions develops students’ thinking skills and fosters responsibility. A student who can manage his time effectively has time to play, study, and relax. Such children are more likely to live successful and balanced lives in the future. Students should go to bed no later than 22:00-23:00. Exposure to light from mobile phones in the evening suppresses the production of the hormone melatonin; as a result, even if a student falls asleep, the brain does not fully rest.

Based on the results of the study, it can be stated that the formation of a daily routine among high school students is of great importance for improving educational quality, personal responsibility, and preparation for independent life. A properly planned daily routine develops students’ effective time-management skills and helps them acquire knowledge. Therefore, cooperation among schools, teachers, and parents is essential in the process of establishing a daily routine for students. It is necessary to provide students with continuous guidance on planning their daily activities and balancing work and leisure. This will contribute to educating responsible, disciplined, and well-rounded individuals who can set clear goals for themselves in the future.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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